

D3.2 Roadmaps for pre-standardization – innovation and capacity building

**Project: Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization
for Boosting the Twin Transition**

Acronym: AFCOS

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Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	101135855	Acronym	AFCOS
Full Title	Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition		
Call and topic identifier	HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-64		
Duration	24 months		
Start Date	1 November 2023	End date	31 October 2025
Website	www.afcos-project.eu		
Coordinator	Cleantech Bulgaria		

Document Information

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Date of approval	18.12.2024
Work Package	WP3 Co-design of roadmaps for pre-standardization
Deliverable	D3.2 Roadmaps for pre-standardization – innovation and capacity building
Nature	Report
Dissemination	External

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1.0	16.12.2024		First draft prepared	TU Sofia
V2.0	18.12.2024		Internal review completed	ASRO

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Acknowledgement

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Introduction

One of the key activities of the AFCOS project is to co-design two roadmaps for boosting the application of standardization for the construction sector as main trigger for achieving the twin transition. Following a structured Methodology for co-design of roadmaps and stepping on the pre-normative research for new building materials performed, the AFCOS consortium developed the roadmaps covering the following topics:

- Standardization as enabler of innovation uptake in the new building materials field (Annex I)
- Capacity building in standardization of new building materials as a booster of new knowledge in industry (Annex II).

The Methodology for co-design of roadmaps covers the following main steps:

Needs analysis

As a start, the key challenges in the construction sector have been identified. The more critical ones among them include the lack of knowledge about standardization and the need for innovation and sustainability. The key areas in which improvements would contribute to boosting the process of uptake of new building materials include education, standardization and innovation.

Stakeholder engagement

Industry, public institutions, universities and other key stakeholders actively participated in the development of the roadmaps as part of the Multistakeholders Research Group formed. Incorporating feedback from stakeholders was planned to improve the relevance and effectiveness of the proposed actions. The integration of the "triple helix", updated to "quintuple helix" model later in the process effectively combines the opinions of industry, government, academia and society for the benefit of the environment.

Results

The roadmaps offer strategic guidance for accelerated standardization, improving human capital and implementing sustainable practices. They are aligned with the European Green Deal and the circular economy objectives.

Aiming to seek validation and applicability of both roadmaps according to different target groups, wide stakeholder dialogue has been facilitated through the organization of 2 stakeholders' consultations on each roadmap. The feedback collected has been summarized within the current document in 2 parts – one for each roadmap, represented as Annex III. The main highlights from the stakeholder consultation process are presented in the section below.

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Key aspects of the roadmaps and the stakeholder consultation process

The developed roadmaps are strategic tools that help plan, coordinate, and execute complex initiatives – in the case of AFCOS: standardization and training activities. They provide a clear vision of the goals, milestones, and actions needed to achieve them. Key benefits of using the roadmaps include:

Stakeholder Coordination

Provide a common framework for action that facilitates communication and collaboration between different groups, including industry, education, public institutions and society. Synchronize the efforts of different participants to avoid duplication of activities or gaps.

Planning and structuring

Divide complex initiatives into clear stages, which help organize resources and track progress. Help identify key actions, deadlines and required resources.

Focus on priorities

Helps identify key needs and challenges that need to be addressed, such as lack of knowledge, innovation or legislative barriers. Focuses on critical areas, such as innovation, sustainability or staff qualifications.

Decision support

Provide analytical approach to evaluate alternatives and make informed decisions. Show possible risks and suggests measures to manage them.

Fostering innovation

Create conditions for the implementation of new technologies and methods by offering flexible solutions for standardization, regulations and training. Support adaptation to rapidly changing market and regulatory requirements.

Measure results

Allow clear definition of expected results and success criteria. Facilitate monitoring of progress and effectiveness of implementation.

In the context of the construction sector, the AFCOS roadmaps help to:

- Improve skills by developing adaptive educational programs.
- Accelerate standardization processes through flexible methods such as CWA or ETA.
- Create platforms for cooperation between industry, public authorities and educational institutions.
- They will help achieve long-term sustainability, increase competitiveness and adapt to new challenges.

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The general impression from the consultations held with external stakeholders is that both roadmaps developed are adequate, practically applicable and meet the expectations of stakeholders. No significant weaknesses have been identified so there is no need for major improvements or adjustments of the roadmaps.

The main conclusion of the consultation process is that they represent an effective tool for overcoming the key challenges in the construction sector, they reflect the needs of the participants, offer concrete solutions and promote innovation and sustainable development. The active stakeholders' participation and the lack of criticism confirm the quality and relevance of the documents. They will be further explored during the next project activities. Detailed highlights from the stakeholder consultation process are presented in Annex III.

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AFCOS

Roadmap “Standardization as enabler of innovation uptake in the new building materials field”

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Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1.0	01.10.2024		First draft	BDS and ASRO
V2.0	07.10.2024		Second draft	BDS and ASRO
V3.0	22.10.2024		Review	CRISCON, RoGBC
V4.0	22.10.2024		Review	BDS
V5.0	05.11.2024		Final draft for SH	CTBG

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I. ABBREVIATIONS

CEN - European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC - European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
ENs - European standards
ETSI - European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU - European Union
IEC - International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO - International Organization for Standardization
MSRG - Multistakeholder research group
TC – Technical Committee
NSB – National Standardization Body
CWA – CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement
EAD - European Assessment Document
ETA -European Technical Assessment
EOTA - European Organisation for Technical Assessment

II. APPLICATION OF THE AFCOS METHODOLOGY FOR CO-DESIGN OF ROADMAPS

The current roadmap has been created based on the Methodology for co-design of roadmaps of the AFCOS project (deliverable D3.1) in accordance with all its principles. This document presents the first roadmap version, since AFCOS’s plan is to co-develop the roadmap in a collaborative process with the stakeholders identified in the Methodology: the roadmap is drafted by the multistakeholder research group already engaged at the previous stage (WP2 – Pre-normative research of legislative framework, existing standards and industrial needs), then wider stakeholder dialogue, in two stakeholders’ consultations on EU level (online), will seek the validation and applicability of the roadmap according to different target groups.

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In this sense, the present document is instrumental to the incoming steps along the participatory process outlined by AFCOS. The **stakeholder engagement** process under the AFCOS project for this specific roadmap started with the project launch and will be running to its end through the creation and operation of a Multistakeholder research group (MSRG). With regard to the current task, we apply the Triple Helix model – onboarding representatives of the industry, academia and policy making institutions in the co-creation process.

Figure 1. The Triple Helix Model

We involve several types of stakeholders in the process of roadmap development on two stages: first the preparation of the roadmap for initial **generation of ideas** (MSRG meetings on national level complementing the internal brainstorming process among the project partners) and second widening the consultations based on the roadmap drafted with the MSRG to EU level consultations through online surveys and interactive webinars. First step will lead to finalizing a full draft of the roadmap, the second step to gathering input on its validation and applicability, to be eventually taken into consideration within the final version of the roadmap.

The development of the current document represents the actual **design** phase. Based on the outcomes of the preparatory stage (WP2) and in reference to the time advantages of two standardization deliverables – CWAs and EADs, the AFCOS team is developing **this roadmap** with special attention to **the pathway to each of the deliverables** allowing manufacturers/owners of innovative product to choose, when relevant and appropriate, the most appropriate procedure on a case-by-case basis. In fact, both of them guarantee flexibility and rapidity if compared to ordinary standard development processes - prerequisites for faster introduction of innovations entering the market.

Following the logic of the co-creation process, the roadmap will go through a phase of **validation and test**. It will be first shared and improved together with the MSRG and, after that, shared in two stakeholders' consultations to be performed on EU level, as mentioned above, in order to seek validation and applicability. The collected feedback (comments, ideas, needs, etc.) will be transferred back into the roadmap to finalize it. This **refinement** process will ensure that it will serve best the needs of the innovative product developers.

The final version of the standardization roadmap will be widely communicated to all interested parties both at national and international level. The "**popularization**" activities will be implemented following the Communication and Dissemination strategy of the AFCOS project with the ultimate objective to achieve visibility among the potential users of the roadmap, e.g.

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academia, researchers, R&I organizations, industry, standards developing organizations, standardization experts, government authorities, etc.

The whole co-design process could be visualized as follows:

Figure 2. Main stages of the roadmap development

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III. SETTING THE STAGE

1. EU Standardization process

The standardization process within the European Union (EU) is a systematic approach aimed at developing, implementing, and maintaining standards across various sectors and industries. European standards (ENs) and standardization deliverables are developed by the three recognized standardization organizations: CEN (European Committee for Standardization), CENELEC (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization) and ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute). In many cases, when possible and relevant, European standards are aligned with the international standards of ISO (International Organization for Standardization) and IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission).

1.1. Types of deliverables

All three EU standardization organizations produce various types of deliverables that serve various purposes and support the Single European Market.

1.1.1. Deliverables of CEN and CENELEC

- **European Standards (EN):** A standard is a document that provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, for common and repeated use. European Standards are a key component of the Single European Market.
- **Harmonized European Standard (hEN):** A standard developed by one of the European standardization organizations (CEN, CENELEC, or ETSI) following a request from the European Commission to one of these organisations for the implementation of the application of European Union harmonization legislation. The references of harmonized standards must be published in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU). These standards are developed to ensure products meet essential requirements set by EU legislation, facilitating the free movement of goods within the European Single Market. Compliance with hENs allows manufacturers to affix the CE marking to their products, indicating conformity with relevant EU directives and regulations.
- **Technical Specification (TS):** A TS is a normative standardization document (a document that provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results), the development of which can be envisaged when various alternatives that would not gather enough as to allow agreement on a European Standard (EN), need to coexist in anticipation of future harmonization, or for providing specifications in experimental circumstances and/or evolving technologies.
- **Technical Report (TR):** A TR is an informative standardization document (a document that describes useful or valuable information or offers help to understand concepts; may include recommendations, suggested good practice; no requirements for conformity included) that provides information on the technical content of standardization work. It may be prepared when it is considered urgent or advisable to provide additional information to the CEN and CENELEC national members, the European Commission, the

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EFTA Secretariat, other governmental agencies or outside bodies.

- **A Harmonization Document (HD):** a HD is a normative document of CENELEC only.
- **A CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA):** A CWA is an agreement developed and approved in a CEN or CENELEC Workshop. The workshop is open to the direct participation of anyone with an interest in the development of the agreement. There is no geographical limit on participation; hence, participants may be from outside Europe. The development of a CWA is fast and flexible, on average between 10-12 months. A CWA does not have the status of a European Standard.
- **CEN and/or CENELEC Guides:** a Guide is a document that gives rules, orientation, advice or recommendations relating to European standardization. However, within the context of the current roadmap they are not a relevant option.

While TSs, TRs and CWAs are considered standardization documents, ENs and hENs are standards. The only deliverables in the above list which are used for CE marking are the hENs, this is especially relevant for construction products under the CPR (Regulation (EU) 305/2011, to date). Of course, hENs can be seen as a medium-term reference for today's innovative construction products, but hENs' development process is significantly longer and complicated, and hardly matches the market fast pace of innovative solutions.

1.1.2. Deliverables of ETSI

Similarly, ETSI produces **European Standards, specifications, reports and guides in the ICT field**, each with its own purpose. They are not explained in detail here as they are not a subject of this roadmap.

1.2. Overview of the typical steps in the development of ENs

- **Identification of needs:** The process begins with identifying the areas where standardization is necessary and submitting a proposal for standard development. This could be driven by technological advancements, regulatory requirements, safety concerns, market demands, or other factors. The main drivers of a new standardization topic are the members of the standardization organizations (in the case of CEN and CENELEC those are the National Standardization Bodies – NSBs)¹. Relevant stakeholders, including industry representatives, regulatory bodies, academics, business and professional associations, consumer groups, environmental and labour organizations, may be involved in this phase. At this step the new work item proposal shall be subject to public commenting to define whether there is an agreement on the need to develop a new standard or to revise an existing one. The need, scope and objectives of the standardization effort should be defined.
- **Preparation and planning:** Once the needs are identified, the standardization process is planned and prepared. This involves assigning or establishing the appropriate technical

¹ <https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=CEN:5>

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working bodies (technical committees/subcommittees, working groups or workshops); determining the participating national standards organizations and the experts that will be involved in the development of the draft deliverable; establishing timelines and milestones; allocating resources; establishing organizational arrangements. An important issue to be addressed is the involvement of different stakeholders of the process.

- **Development of a draft standard:** Standards are developed based on technical expertise, scientific research, industry best practices, and input from stakeholders. This phase typically involves drafting the standard, conducting technical reviews, assessments and discussions, resolving conflicting viewpoints, and achieving consensus among participants of the working group or the technical body.
- **Consultation and consensus building:** Draft standards are subject to consultation with stakeholders to gather feedback and address any concerns or suggestions for improvement. During the Enquiry stage the ESOs Members (NSBs) have the obligation to make available the draft standard for public comments. This consultation process aims to ensure that the standards reflect the needs and interests of all relevant parties and facilitate consensus building among diverse stakeholders.
- **Approval and adoption:** Once consensus is reached and a positive voting outcome is registered, the draft standards are formally approved by the relevant standardization organizations. In the EU context, standards may be adopted as European Standards (ENs) by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC), or the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), depending on the sector. Unlike international standards, which don't necessarily require national adoptions in order to be used by the end-users, a European Standard shall be implemented by the CEN and CENELEC members – the national standards organizations - as national standards.
- **Publication and distribution:** Approved standards are published and made available to stakeholders, industry players, regulators, and the public in compliance with the copyright rules applicable to the respective deliverable. CEN and CENELEC standards and deliverables, their national adoptions and other technical related deliverables and publications are covered and protected by copyright. The standard body issuing the standard has the property and exploitation rights on it. Standards are typically listed in online catalogues (online databases) of the respective standardization organization, and offered to the standards users for purchase through online or physical webstores to ensure easy and fast access and distribution.
- **Implementation and Compliance:** Standards users are encouraged to implement the standards within their organizations or industries. Compliance with standards may be voluntary or mandatory (by exception), depending on regulatory requirements, market expectations or contractual agreements. Implementation may require training, auditing, conformity assessment (inspection, testing, certification), and other measures to ensure adherence to the standards.

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- **Monitoring and Review:** The implementation of standards is monitored to assess their effectiveness, technology and market relevance and impact. Typically, every 5 years a published standard is subject to a systematic review process. Feedback from stakeholders, performance data, market trends, and technological advancements are considered during the systematic review stage to ensure the standards remain relevant, up-to-date, and aligned with state-of-the-art technology, as well as with the evolving needs and practices. The outcome of the systematic review stage might lead to confirmation of the relevance of the standard or deliverable, withdrawal, decision for revision. Unlike ENs, CWAs are valid for 3 years only. Once the three-year validity period has expired, a review has to be made and a CWA could be confirmed for another 3 years (only once), revised, withdrawn, or converted into another deliverable – e.g. upgraded to TS or EN.

Figure 3. Process of standardization for EN standards

- **Alignment between European and International standardization through cooperation:** The European standardization organizations CEN and CENELEC actively cooperate with international standardization organizations ISO and IEC to align European standards with

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global best practices. This alignment enhances interoperability, facilitates trade, and promotes the acceptance of European standards worldwide.

By following this standardized process, the EU ensures the development and implementation of high-quality standards that promote innovation, competitiveness, safety, and sustainability across various sectors while fostering harmonization and cooperation at the national, European, and international levels.

	General	Electrotechnical	Telecommunication
International			
European (regional)			

Figure 4. Correspondence between European and International Standardization

2. THE JOURNEY OF INNOVATION: STEPS WHERE STANDARDIZATION CAN ACT AS AN ENABLER FOR QUICKER AND EASIER PROCESS

We want to provide guidance here on what is the standardization deliverable that can best meet innovation’s needs. As illustrated above, two main fast-track deliverables show a development time which is generally compatible with fast-pace innovation. We’ll treat them separately, underlining advantages and disadvantages of each path.

2.1. CEN/CENELEC WORKSHOP AGREEMENTS (CWA)

Throughout the development process described above, standardization organizations follow the CEN-CENELEC principles: transparency, openness and sustainable development, impartiality and consensus, effectiveness and relevance, coherence. These principles encourage the participation of various stakeholders to ensure that standards represent a balanced and consensus-based approach, promoting their wide acceptance and adoption.

It's important to note that the **standardization process** usually **takes a significant amount of time**, spanning several months or several years, depending on the complexity, type and scope of the deliverable and the principles that need to be followed. For example, for a regular standard it takes about three years from first proposal to final publication. The reason is the involvement of multiple stakeholders, and the rigorous consultation process are crucial in producing effective and relevant standards that benefit society, industries, and consumers.

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On the contrary, innovation requires quick actions, outcomes and agile procedures to go to the market. Markets and industries, for which innovations are important, usually are dissatisfied with the long procedures of standards development. They require more flexible and rapid procedures for development of a reference document, which could timely enable the market uptake of innovative solutions and facilitate further innovations in the market. On the other hand, innovative solutions might have not reached a sufficient degree of reliability and maturity, which is needed for a European Standard to be developed. Finally, placing construction products on the market requires CE marking, with some exceptions based on national qualifications and certifications (such as concrete and steel reinforcement bars, for example). CE marking is key to companies willing to place innovative construction products on the market. In lack of an applicable hEN, the potential development time of a new standard often becomes an obstacle moving the innovators towards alternative options.

Taking all that into consideration, innovations might reach towards a more flexible standardization deliverable, available at European level, that is, as anticipated above, the CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA). CWA is a standardization document that could be quickly developed and agreed on more easily in order to meet an immediate necessity. The CWA process provides for direct participation of interested parties and experts, which do not need to be assigned and empowered by a national standardization organization in order to participate in the drafting of the document. That is why CWA is a proper and preferred tool for standardization of the results delivered by research and innovation projects. In addition, at a later stage it could be “upgraded” to a more formal document, for example Technical Specification of European Standard.

With reference to the development process described above, **CWAs differ from European standards in the following aspects:**

- While standards are developed in Technical Committees with members from national delegations, CWAs are elaborated by temporary working groups according to CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 at workshops where individual interested parties could participate;
- CWA’s development rules provide for direct and voluntary participation of stakeholders regardless of their participation in national TCs and they are an excellent forum for experts from R&I organizations, academia and industry to offer their innovative solutions for standardization;
- The workshops are open to any company, inside or outside Europe;
- CWAs are developed under lighter and more rapid procedures, compared to regular standards;
- The working tools of the workshop are more agile, and flexible timeline and electronic communication and working tools could be preferred;
- Public consultation is not a mandatory stage of the CWA’s development. It is optional but highly recommended in order to ensure as transparent process as possible.

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- The approval of the document is subject to a decision of the registered participants in the workshop, and it is not subject to vote by CEN and CENELEC national members.

The figure below illustrates the **advantages of CWAs when innovative solutions need to be standardized.**

Figure 5. Advantages of CWA

2.1.1. DEVELOPMENT OF CEN AND/OR CENELEC WORKSHOP AGREEMENT

The development of CWAs is described in details in CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 “CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreements – A rapid way to standardization”. The process that is going to be explained below is based on its third edition of March 2024. The Guide emphasizes that CWAs could be the preferred way of standardization particularly in cases of innovative solutions, which need faster market uptake, or assurance of interoperability and compatibility, or in cases where the Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) is not sufficient enough to start developing a European Standard (EN).

CWA could be addressed to a specific technology, a process or a specific methodology, or any other kind of innovative solution, and it is not necessary to address an innovation product in its completeness.

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Definition of CWA: Guide 29 defines this type of standardization document as ***“CEN and/or CENELEC deliverable, developed by a CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop, which reflects an agreement between identified individuals and organizations responsible for its contents, and which is made available by CEN and/or CENELEC in at least one of the official languages”***.

The main actors and responsible persons for CWA creation are the participants in the Workshop. The CEN/CENELEC Workshop is a temporary group open to the participation of any interested parties and it does not necessarily involve CEN/CENELEC national members or their representatives, or related CEN or CENELEC technical bodies.

The Workshop has a short-term task, which should be clearly specified in the “objectives and scopes” section of its project plan.

A CWA is a deliverable that provides flexibility also in terms of its format. It may take various forms – for example, it may be developed as a text file or as computer code. On the one hand, it is an appropriate tool to meet an immediate market, technology or industry need, and on the other hand, it could be a fast track to future standardization activities, as mentioned above.

When it comes to innovative project outcomes or solutions, CWA offers additional advantages, compared to ENs: possibility to name the persons and organizations who participated in the CWA’s development in the Foreword of the document; the CWA’s development time span could fit into the timeframe of EU funded research and innovation projects in order to deliver verified and validated results.

It is important to emphasize that during the CWA creation all participants should be aware that a CWA shall not be in conflict with any EN (of Harmonization Document for CENELEC) and it is advisable to seek collaboration from a CEN or CENELEC technical body which is dealing with the related subjects. A support by a technical committee, for example, might ensure future sustainability of the CWA, if the topic is included in the committee’s future work programme.

It should also be taken into consideration that a CWA could not be used to support European legislative requirements. It cannot also address safety matters and if a CWA is intended to address security, a risk analysis shall be carried out.

The figure below illustrates the main stages of initiating and developing a CWA. All those steps are used as a point of reference for developing the roadmap on enabling innovations uptake in the new building materials field through standardization.

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Figure 6. CWA Process.

Source: CEN-CENELEC Guide 29:2024

2.2. THE EUROPEAN TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT (ETA) AND THE EUROPEAN ASSESSMENT DOCUMENT (EAD)

Another option for fast-track standardization and innovation uptake of research outcomes in the new building materials field, which needs to be considered, is given by **the deliverables of the European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA)**.

The European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA) is a Europe-wide association of Technical Assessment Bodies for construction products established under the Construction Products Regulation (CPR).

EOTA is a non-profit organization, which provides the framework for the European Technical Assessment (ETA) of construction products to ensure consistent product performance information throughout Europe. The EOTA network is the only platform which allows European manufacturers of innovative or non-standard construction products to bring their products to the European market with CE marking. As stated in the previous chapter for standards, CE marking is crucial for construction products, with minor exceptions. In other words, in lack of a

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hENs ETAs are well known and largely used tools towards CE marking and product market placement on EU scale.

The basis of the ETA approach is the European Assessment Documents (EADs) developed within EOTA. EADs were introduced by the Regulation (EU) 305/2011 to replace former ETAGs (ETA guidelines).

EOTA has been established under the Construction Products Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 and brought together the bodies designated by the Member States of the European Union and the European Economic Area to issue ETAs - the Technical Assessment Bodies (TABs).

The European Technical Assessment (ETA) provides an independent Europe-wide procedure for assessing the essential performance characteristics of non-standard construction products.

The ETA offers manufacturers a **voluntary route to CE marking**, when the product is not or not fully covered by a harmonized standard (hEN) under the Construction Products Regulation (EU) 305/2011. CE marking based on the ETA allows manufacturers to freely market their product on the entire European internal market and introduce innovative products and new product features within short timeframes. **The ETA procedure offers an array of further advantages:**

- The ETA route is an efficient procedure ensuring the shortest possible processing time.
- ETAs are recognized throughout Europe in all countries participating in the ETA procedure. The ETA also has a high international standing.
- Only independent Technical Assessment Bodies (TABs) may issue ETAs. TABs are designated for the relevant product area by the EU Member and Partner States in accordance with the Construction Products Regulation (EU) No 305/2011. The independent assessment strengthens the credibility of the product performance information, enhances market transparency and builds customer trust.
- ETAs provide reliable product performance information that is comparable across Europe based on European Assessment Documents (EADs).

An European Assessment Document (EAD), is a **harmonized technical specification** developed by EOTA as the basis for ETAs.

In combination with the ETA, the EAD provides manufacturers with a way to CE marking for construction products that are not or not fully covered by a harmonized European standard under the Construction Products Regulation (EU) 305/2011. EADs have many benefits for construction product manufacturers:

- EADs can be tailored to a construction product;
- The EAD development procedure could be kept confidential upon request to protect the manufacturer's competitive advantage;
- After citation in the EU Official Journal, EADs can be downloaded for free from the EOTA

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website.

The EAD development procedure is initiated by a manufacturer's request for ETA, when harmonised criteria for the assessment of the product's performance are missing. The procedure is handled by a Technical Assessment Body - TAB, which the manufacturer has chosen. The TAB is supported by the EOTA network of highly qualified Technical Assessment experts. There are 8 development stages according to Annex II of the Construction Products Regulation (EU) No 305/2011:

1. ETA request of a manufacturer
2. Consultation of work and assessment programme; contract between the TAB and the manufacturer
3. Agreement on the final work programme and information to the EC
4. Drafting of the EAD
5. Adoption of draft EAD by the manufacturer, the responsible TAB and EOTA
6. Finalization of the EU legislative procedures (extensions and delays, where relevant)
7. EAD adoption by EOTA and the EC
8. Issuing of ETA and publication of reference of final EAD in Official Journal

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The 8 stages of the EAD development

	Stage designation	Who is involved?
1.	ETA request	Manufacturer & responsible TAB (RTAB)
2.	Consultation of work and assessment programme and contract between TAB and manufacturer	RTAB, EOTA
3.	Agreed final work programme & information to the European Commission (EC)	Manufacturer & RTAB & EOTA
4.	EAD drafting	Manufacturer & RTAB & EOTA
5.	Adoption of draft EAD	Manufacturer & RTAB & EOTA
6.	Extensions and delays for the finalisation of EU legislative procedures, where relevant	European Commission, Standing Committee on Construction (SCC), Council, European Parliament
7.	EAD adoption	EOTA & European Commission
8.	Issuing of ETA and publication of reference of final EAD in Official Journal of the European Union	RTAB & EOTA & European Commission

Source: EOTA

Figure 7. EAD development stages

The table below displays a **comparison between ENs, CWAs and ETAs/EADs**, which depicts the advantages of CWAs and ETAs/EADs and clearly justifies why those documents would be the preferred standardization deliverables, which this roadmap addresses.

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Table 1. Comparison between EN, CWA and ETA/EAD:

Elements of the development process	EN	CWA	ETA/EAD
Procedures	Rigorous procedure with strict timing for public consultations and enquiry	More flexible and light procedures	Strictly defined procedures
Timing	Usually takes 3 years	Fast track – 10-12 months on average; time could be reduced even to 6 months, depending on the readiness	Fast track – The usual timeline for the development of an EAD set out in the Construction Products Regulation is 9 months .
Participation in development	National delegations of CEN and CENELEC members	Direct participation of experts and stakeholders Open to any company or organization	EOTA experts Member states representatives Manufacturers European Commission
Approval	CEN and CENELEC members	Participating experts	EOTA European Commission
National adoption and publication	Mandatory	Optional	Not relevant
Allows for CE marking	Yes	No	Yes
Stakeholders involvement	Full open and transparent public consultation (manufacturer, end users, academia, researchers, consumer protection etc.)	From case to case, depends on the working group members	Only the manufacturer (group of) who asked for, EOTA and the EC

3. THE INCOMING CPR: SOME NOVELTY ELEMENTS

We don't mean to provide here a full analysis of the new CPR, which is expected to entry into force soon, whose provisions will become effective along an articulated transition phase. Rather, we summarize here key information about the main novelties it is going to bring, since they're relevant for the twin transition.

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The legislative process for the new Construction Products Regulation (CPR) commenced with the European Commission's proposal on March 30, 2022. This proposal aimed to update and replace the existing Regulation (EU) No 305/2011, addressing issues such as market fragmentation, complex legal frameworks, and the need for alignment with green and digital transitions.

The proposal was referred to the Committee on the Internal Market and Consumer Protection (IMCO) on May 18, 2022. Following this, a provisional agreement was reached by the European Parliament and the Council on December 13, 2023. The Coreper, representing Member States' ambassadors, endorsed this agreement on February 2, 2024. Subsequently, the IMCO approved the proposal on February 13, 2024. The final approval by the European Parliament was granted on April 10, 2024.

The regulation now awaits formal adoption by the Council of the European Union. Once adopted, it will be published in the Official Journal of the European Union and enter into force on a specified date.

The new CPR introduces several significant changes compared to its predecessor, Regulation (EU) No 305/2011. It expands the scope to include reused, 3D-printed construction products, and pre-fabricated one-family houses. The European Commission is empowered to adopt technical specifications if the standardisation system fails to deliver. New product requirements are introduced, covering environmental, functional, and safety aspects. A harmonised zone for product requirements is established, aiming to reduce regulatory discrepancies among Member States.

Manufacturers are now required to provide a declaration of conformity in addition to a declaration of performance. The regulation defines general sustainability requirements, which will be further detailed in Commission acts. Simplification and exemption provisions are introduced for micro-enterprises, and the enforcement powers of market surveillance authorities are strengthened. Additionally, the regulation aligns with the proposed regulation on ecodesign requirements for sustainable products by introducing a digital product passport.

The implementation timeline for the new CPR will span over a long transition period. The regulation will enter into force 20 days after publication and will apply to products placed on the market 24 months after entry into force. A transitional period of 36 months will be provided to allow manufacturers to adapt to the new requirements. During this period, products that comply with the current CPR (305/2011) will still be allowed to be placed on the market. Temporary provisions will also be introduced to allow for the continued use of existing product certificates and declarations of performance. The implementation timeline, though, is more articulated (for example in reference to digital passports), we reference the reader today to the text approved by the EU parliament on April 10th 2024 for all relevant details.²

² [European Parliament legislative resolution of 10 April 2024 on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products, amending Regulation \(EU\) 2019/1020 and repealing Regulation \(EU\) 305/2011 \(COM\(2022\)0144 – C9-0129/2022 – 2022/0094\(COD\)\)](#)

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The entry into force of the new CPR is expected to happen in the coming months and will mark a significant step forward in the EU's efforts to improve the safety and sustainability of construction products.

IV. CO-DESIGN PROCEDURE OF THE ROADMAP FOR STANDARDIZATION AS ENABLER OF INNOVATION UPTAKE IN THE NEW BUILDING PRODUCTS FIELD

Since the main goal of this document is to set out where standardization can act as an enabler for quicker and easier process, we enter the steps and timings of each pre-identified pathway (CWA and EAD) and highlight when and how the innovative content can be valued and should be proven. From a practical standpoint, this leads to two paths (CEN/EAD) here a roadmap for CWA and a roadmap for the EAD/ETA, as they respond to different needs and purposes.

1. HOW TO CHOOSE THE MOST APPROPRIATE STANDARDIZATION PROCEDURE FOR INNOVATIONS

The standardization of new innovative building products is an ambitious objective starting from a compliance check with regulatory frameworks regarding the specific product, including the Construction Products Regulation and other relevant regulatory frameworks followed by identification of applicable harmonized standards. If there is no such standard available, alternative options could be sought.

In this document we have identified two possible pathways to fast-track standardization procedures. In the following we set out the steps and tasks to be completed for answering the question – how innovations can be faster applied in practice with the help of standardization with the aim to ease the process and create the conditions for faster commercialization of innovation. As we have seen, compared to the common standardization process in EU which takes up to 3 years, the development of EAD or CWA will take between 9 and 10 - 12 months. Both deliverables have also other specific advantages as described above so each manufacturer/owner of innovation could select and follow the most appropriate procedure for its case.

The development process of each of these deliverables - CWA and EAD - differ significantly in terms of purpose, implementation process, stakeholders involved, outcome, level of formality, confidentiality and adoption which is also a kind of advantage offering different procedures for different types of products to be standardized.

Besides the main target group of our roadmap – the innovation owners that initiate the respective procedure, there are also other target groups to benefit from the proposed flexible standardization procedures to be implemented as enablers of innovation uptake in the new building products field:

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Figure 8. Target groups

The Roadmap on standardization as enabler of innovation uptake in the new building materials field offers the steps which an individual person or an organization could undertake to walk the road to faster delivery of an innovation result to the market.

We provide guidance in reference to the two standardization tools identified above, that is for standardization through CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA) and for technical assessment through ETA/EAD procedure.

The guidance hereby provided does not explain in detail all organizational and technical aspects of CWA or ETA/EAD development, but rather proposes concrete actions, which the innovation owner should undertake, through answering the questions – **WHAT** to do, **WHO** is responsible and should be involved, what the timeframe is (**TIME**).

At the very beginning the innovation owner has to choose whether to focus his/her efforts on submission of a proposal for CWA or may prefer to use the ETA/EAD option.

Here are some considerations and hints **how to choose between CWA and ETA/EAD**:

- The manufacturers of innovation products for the building sector can choose one of the two options for fast standardization and market uptake on the basis of their own analysis

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of the pros and cons of the CWA and ETA/EAD. In both cases they must ensure that their product conforms all the requirements of the Construction Products Regulation (EU) 305/2011 (CPR). The purpose of the CWA or ETA/EAD would be to ensure their customers and stakeholders that incorporating their innovation products in the construction works complies with the conditions for basic works requirements envisaged in CPR.

- ETA/EAD set a path to CE marking when the product is not or not fully covered by a harmonized standard (hEN) under the CPR, which is key for construction products.
- ETA/EAD procedure is applicable only for manufacturers.
- Developed and approved EAD becomes a harmonized technical specification (similarly to harmonized standards) once published in the Official Journal of the EU.
- The EOTA network is the only platform which allows European manufacturers of innovative or **non-standard construction products** to bring their products to the European market with **CE marking**
- A CWA is not a possible candidate for citation in OJEU.
- The ETA provides the manufacturer with the possibility to affix CE marking on the product, when the product is not or not fully covered by a harmonized standard (hEN) under the CPR.
- The route to ETA/EAD typically requires very detailed technical specification and documentation.
- CWA is at the bottom of the hierarchy of the standardization documents.
- If the CWA content is developed in the format of a technical specification, it could provide information for conformity assessment of the product, but CWA does not underpin CE marking. This will only be possible if the CWA will be considered as the basis for a future European standard.
- Usually, CWA is developed with the aim to be, at a later stage, converted into a Technical Specification (TS) or a European Standard (EN).
- The manufacturer does not pay for the EAD development, but the costs for issuing an ETA, might be rather high.

Below is provided a summarized information on the advantages and disadvantages of CWA and ETA/EAD.

Table 2. Comparison between CWA and ETA/EAD

	Advantages	Disadvantages
CWA	Fast development	CWA is not equal to a standard. It is a

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	<p>Need to reach agreement among participants</p> <p>Possibility to conversion into another deliverable, as a TS or a TR or a European standard</p> <p>Does not entail significant costs</p>	<p>standardization document.</p> <p>No right to affix CE marking</p> <p>No possible candidate for citation in OJEU</p>
ETA/EAD	<p>Fast development</p> <p>Harmonized technical specification</p> <p>No need to reach agreement of external stakeholders</p> <p>Right to affix CE marking (together with all applicable further obligations to the manufacturer, including the ones involving notified body)</p>	<p>Higher costs for obtaining ETA</p> <p>EAD needs to be published in Official Journal of the EU</p>

2. ROADMAP FOR STANDARDIZATION THROUGH CEN AND/OR CENELEC WORKSHOP AGREEMENT (CWA) DEVELOPMENT

1. Action 1: Clearly define innovation product and prepare

WHAT

Define its characteristics, production technology, testing methods, advantages, argumentation about why it is innovative, what advantages, benefits, etc. it brings, but also what limitations or drawbacks exist, prepare about patents (if any), and all that might be needed to substantiate your innovation.

Clearly identify Technology Readiness Level (TRL).

Below is a table briefly describing the technology readiness levels as set by the EC to serve the purposes of EU funded research projects.

It is useful to indicate the TRL level of the research / development result of innovation products and to identify whether your innovation has reached a sufficient level of maturity so that it could be brought to the market through standardization. Usually, a CWA should start at a TRL 5 or TRL 6, and on a case-by-case basis it might start at TRL 4.

Table 3. Technology Readiness Levels

TRL 1	Basic principles observed
TRL 2	Technology concept formulated
TRL 3	Experimental proof of concept

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TRL 4	Technology validated in lab
TRL 5	Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 6	Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 7	System prototype demonstration in operational environment
TRL 8	System complete and qualified
TRL 9	Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

WHO

The innovation owner.

Investigate and identify what organizations/individuals might be supporter and collaborators in the standardization process. Those might be contractors, suppliers, designers, architects, material production operators, laboratories (or other conformity assessment players), business associations, researchers, etc.

TIME

Proposal of a timeframe for this initial step (action 1) is not relevant, as this depends entirely on specific level of preparedness.

2. Action 2: Investigate what collaboration and support could the initiative receive from a standards making organization or technical body

WHAT

Check whether and what technical bodies exist at the European standardization organization CEN (here is a list of CEN Technical bodies - <https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=CEN:6>) and at the national standards development body (<https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=CEN:5>) and select the ones that deal with similar or relevant technical fields, and which might be of help and support.

Get into contact with the national standards development body to ask for support.

Preferably, find and involve an experienced standardization expert to support the entire process.

WHO

The innovation owner and if possible, close supporters or collaborators, who will be involved in the standardization activities.

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TIME

Proposal of a timeframe is not relevant, as this depends entirely on specific level of preparedness.

3. Action 3: Initiate the procedure

WHAT

Every CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop shall be supported by a secretariat from a CEN and/or CENELEC national member. In the case of new building products and materials a secretariat from a CEN TC is required.

The innovation owners shall ask his/her/its national standards body, member of CEN, to become a secretariat of the Workshop, or if it is not possible, to help find one. In cases where the innovative product is a result of a joint research project, the best partner for that would be the participating standardization organization, if there is one involved in the project.

In cases where a CEN national member cannot be identified, it is possible to contact CCMC (CEN and CENELEC Management Centre) to help. The concept of the intended Workshop and other relevant information should be sent. CCMC will launch a 30-day call for candidates among its members to become a Workshop secretariat.

Being the innovator a Workshop proposer, in conjunction with the Workshop secretariat, he/she/it shall be responsible for defining and agreeing on any financial arrangements, including any participation fees, necessary for the completion of the project plan.

WHO

The involved participants in this step are the Workshop initiator (the innovator), supported by a national standardization body, member of CEN, and CCMC.

TIME

Proposal of a timeframe is not relevant, as this depends on specific level of preparedness and contacts established. In case CCMC support is needed to find a secretariat, it should be considered this adds at least 30-45 days.

4. Action 4: Prepare the necessary starting documents

WHAT

Prepare a Workshop description form, which contains two parts: Part A – Workshop summary, and Part B – Project Plan. The Workshop summary shall provide information of the main aspects of the Workshop and allow the identification of the relevant stakeholders and bodies to be informed when launching the Workshop.

It's necessary to answer questions, such as: "Does the proposed Workshop fall within the scope of existing CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Bodies" and if so – you to name them; if there are any

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technical bodies that might be interested in the proposed matter, to involve them; what is the proposal for CWA (title, scope and do you think there might be any contradiction with an existing EN), etc.

Part B – Project Plan explains the background, objectives, and details of the work to be done in the Workshop. The innovator shall fill in information about Workshop proposer and Workshop participants; the motivation for the proposed Workshop, market environment, legal environment, relation to EU funded projects, financing, information about existing standards and standard related activities and documents, possible liaison with CEN technical bodies.

The innovator shall propose a Workshop programme with concrete tasks and schedule; to describe the planning of resources and rules of cooperation, incl. decision making process and dissemination and participation strategy.

The Workshop description form shall be submitted by the Workshop secretariat to CCMC for allocation to a CCMC project manager.

WHO

The Workshop description form shall be prepared jointly by the Workshop proposer and the Workshop secretariat.

Stakeholders: An important part of this document is to identify stakeholders. The project plan needs to suggest how to disseminate and involve a wider range of interested parties throughout the development of the CWA and after its publication. It is advisable to include a strategy defining how and when participants, other standardization bodies and other stakeholders can be informed of the work and contribute to it.

Possible stakeholders might be: industry players (e.g. manufacturers of building products, suppliers of materials for the construction sector, investment design engineers, construction companies); professional associations in the construction sector; government agencies; conformity assessment bodies; environmental NGOs; research organizations and academia representatives; consumer organizations.

TIME

There is no predefine deadline, it should be noticed that if the description form identifies that the Workshop falls within the scope of an existing CEN (and/or CENELEC) technical body, the Workshop description form shall be submitted to it by the Workshop secretariat for consultation.

The consultation with the relevant CEN Technical body might take between 30 and 45 days. The relevant technical body is expected to answer the questions “Does the proposed CWA conflict with a published EN?” and “Are there arguments against the development of the planned CWA?”.

If the technical body responds positively to the CWA being developed, the CEN Workshop proposal may go forward.

If the technical body has objections to the launch of the Workshop, the proposal shall be submitted to the CEN (and/or CENELEC) Technical Board(s) for decision. If the Technical Board

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has objections or concerns, CCMC starts consultation process to settle those. The review of the Workshop description form and the consultations to follow might take additional 30-45 days.

5. Action 5: Prepare the kick-off meeting of the Workshop

WHAT

After receiving positive feedback to the Workshop description form, or even in advance, the innovator should prepare the kick-off meeting. The kick-off meeting could be held in person in one of the CEN (and/or CENELEC) National Members' countries or online.

It is key to ensure the necessary organizational arrangements, to prepare the kick-off meeting agenda, venue, schedule, etc., and to submit the agenda to the CCMC project manager.

WHO

The preparatory arrangements are joint responsibility of the Workshop proposer and secretariat. The submission is a task of the Workshop secretariat.

Stakeholders: the innovator shall ensure that key relevant stakeholders are available for participation in the kick-off meeting of the Workshop.

TIME

Depending on the format chosen for the kick-off meeting (in person or online) this step may take between a few weeks and several months, then it is important to start as early as possible.

6. Action 6: Follow the Workshop announcement

WHAT

The Workshop secretariat shall provide CCMC with the agenda of the kick-off meeting and other documents relevant for the registration of participants to the kick-off meeting. CCMC announces the kick-off meeting on the CEN and CENELEC website, along with posting the Workshop description form, the call for experts and interested parties to register for the Workshop, the kick-off meeting agenda and, if available, the first draft CWA, for submission of comments.

WHO

This stage is responsibility of the Workshop secretariat and CCMC.

However, it is advisable the Workshop proposer follows closely this stage in order to have the complete picture.

TIME

Within 15 days after approval of the Workshop description form, CCMC publishes the posts on its website. Interested parties have a 30-day commenting period.

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7. Action 7: Actively contribute to the kick-off meeting

WHAT

When the time for comments and registration of interest passes, the kick-off meeting can take place.

Meanwhile, it is strongly recommended that the innovator and the Workshop secretariat engage relevant stakeholders for participation in the Workshop and the CWA development. In addition, they should consider and resolve any comments received on the Workshop project plan.

At the kick-off meeting, the Project plan shall be agreed on and Workshop Chair shall be appointed by the participants. The chair is to be nominated by the Workshop secretariat.

The Project plan shall be respected by all Workshop participants after its adoption. Joining of new participants at a later stage is possible only upon agreement of the Workshop.

Based on the agreements reached during the kick-off meeting the Workshop Secretariat shall submit a New Work Item (NWI) form to CCMC to be registered in the database and receive identifier (CWA xxxx).

WHO

The main responsibility at this stage is carried by the Workshop secretariat.

However, as a Workshop proposer, it is advisable that the innovator supports and collaborates with the secretariat in all necessary preparations.

TIME

Defining timeframe is not relevant for the innovator, as the work duration of this stage depends on the agreements and the secretariat. CEN and CENELEC Guide 29 does not define deadlines for those arrangements.

CEN-CENELEC Guide 29, to which reference is made here for any further detail, explicitly describes the responsibilities and tasks of the Workshop secretariat and chair. As this roadmap is targeted primarily to what actions could be taken by innovation owners, those technical aspect are not described in the present document. It should be reminded that the Guide sets a requirement for the Workshop secretariat to engage with identified European and international technical bodies, either interested or in the same domain. Once the CWA is published, the Workshop secretariat shall submit it to the identified CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Bodies in the same scope for assessment in view of its possible transformation into another deliverable, and to the ones identified as interested, for information.

8. Actions 8: Actively participate and contribute to the drafting of the CWA

WHAT

The draft CWA is developed by the Workshop participants.

Working meetings are organized for elaboration and discussion of the draft content.

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This is the core moment for the innovator to bring the innovative product closer to the market. The innovator should actively participate in all working meetings and offer proper content. It is important to notice that the proposal of content for the CWA must not only focus on the underlying innovation, but should be set out in such a way that it could achieve agreement and approval at a later stage.

The innovator should be prepared with the proper argumentation, testing methods/results, proofing, etc. to convince the participating stakeholders and to meet possible questions, debates, controversial issues or objections. The innovator should, of course, participate in all debates of the Workshop participants.

When the draft is ready, it shall be sent for internal consultation to all Workshop participants, as well as to relevant technical bodies (if any). The comments received shall be taken into consideration. When internal agreement on a final draft CWA is reached, the drafting phase shall be closed and the final draft shall be submitted to the CCMC project manager.

WHO

The responsibility of the drafting process is shared by the Workshop secretariat, participants and chair.

Although formally the Workshop proposer is not directly engaged with an obligation at this stage, he/she/it must be active and intensely contribute to the elaboration of the content, because his/her/its innovation is placed in the centre of the draft standardization document.

The agreements reached in the project plan should be followed and all relevant interested parties must be informed and involved in the process.

TIME

Time necessary for the drafting and internal consultation is defined in the timetable agreed by the Workshop participants. The timing of this step also depends on the time needed for reaching agreements on the content.

The final working draft, after internal consultation, will be sent to relevant technical bodies, a commenting period of 30 days is recommended.

9. Actions 9: Support the public commenting

WHAT

The CWA development procedure does not necessarily require a public commenting phase to be envisaged. However, it is highly recommended to provide the draft CWA for comments in order to ensure not only transparency, but also to receive suggestions for improvement, insights, and proposals which might help to improve the document.

Positive feedback of the proposed draft document from the interested stakeholders might serve as a validation tool for the innovation and support its market acceptance.

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It is advisable for the innovator to seek for the opinions of potential contractors, collaborators, and all individuals or organizations that might be of help to the uptake of your innovation product.

After closing the external consultation period, all comments received on the final draft CWA shall be considered and resolved and a revised draft shall be submitted to the Workshop for approval. The revision stage is considered complete when the Workshop participants reach final agreement on the content of the revised draft.

WHO

The organization of the public commenting phase is a responsibility of the Workshop secretariat, chair and CCMC, but your role as Workshop proposer is also very important, as described above.

TIME

The duration of the public commenting phase (if any) shall be 30 days.

To save time the Workshop may decide that this public commenting phase will be organized in parallel with the Workshop's commenting round on the final draft.

10. Actions 10: Follow the process of approval and publication

WHAT

When an agreement on the final draft is reached, the Workshop approves the CWA. The Workshop secretariat shall submit the agreed CWA document to CCMC, which shall proceed as soon as possible with the publication.

The national standards bodies, members of CEN and/or CENELEC, are not obliged to adopt the CWA, but they notify CCMC on whether and how they will make the CWA available in their countries.

The distribution of CWAs is subject to copyrights.

WHO

This phase is responsibility of the Workshop secretariat and CCMC.

The innovator follows the process until the publication of the CWA.

TIME

The CWA will be published by CCMC as soon as possible after its approval.

All the actions are summarized in the table below showing the description of each action, and the responsible person(s), supporters and stakeholders as well as the timeframe.

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Table 4. CWA Development Procedure

Action No	1: DEFINE the innovation product and PREPARE	2: INVESTIGATE possible collaboration and support	3: INITIATE THE PROCEDURE	4: PREPARE DOCUMENTS	5: PREPARE KICK-OFF MEETING of the Workshop	6: FOLLOW the Workshop announcement	7: CONTRIBUTE to the kick-off meeting	8: PARTICIPATE AND CONTRIBUTE to the drafting of the CWA	9: SUPPORT the public commenting	10: FOLLOW the process of approval and publication
Description	Define the product's characteristics, production technology, testing methods, advantages, argumentation about why it is innovative, what advantages, benefits, etc. it brings, limitations or drawbacks; defining the TRL!	Check the technical bodies at CEN and at the national standards development body. Establish contacts and ask for support	Ask your national standards body (member of CEN) to become Workshop secretariat. Otherwise, ask for support from CEN.	Prepare the Workshop description form	Prepare the kick-off meeting	CCMC announces the kick-off meeting on the CEN and CENELEC website	Actively participate in the kick-off meeting. When agreements are reached, a New Work Item (NWI) form is to be submitted to CCMC to be registered in the database with identifier (CWA xxxx)	The draft CWA is developed by the Workshop participants. Contribute with your know-how	Public commenting phase is not obligatory, but it is highly recommended. Receive comments, suggestions for improvement, insights, and proposals which might help for improvement of the document. All comments received on the final draft CWA shall be considered and resolved and a revised draft shall be submitted to the Workshop for approval	When an agreement on the final draft is reached, the CWA is approved by the Workshop. The Workshop secretariat submits the agreed CWA document to CCMC. The new CWA is published
Responsible (main actors of the CWA development stage)	innovation owner	innovation owner	Workshop initiator	Workshop proposer and Workshop secretariat	Workshop proposer and secretariat	Workshop secretariat and CCMC	Workshop secretariat	Workshop secretariat, participants and chair	Workshop secretariat, chair and CCMC	Workshop secretariat and CCMC
Supporters and stakeholders	Contractors, suppliers, designers, architects, material production operators, conformity assessment operators, business associations, researchers, etc.	close supporters or collaborators; standards development organizations, national standards body, their technical bodies	national standards body, member of CEN, and CCMC	identified stakeholders-e.g. industry players, professional associations in the construction sector; government agencies; conformity assessment bodies; environmental NGOs; research organizations and academia representatives; consumer organizations	ensure participation of most important stakeholders	Workshop proposer	Workshop proposer	Workshop proposer and all relevant interested parties	Workshop proposer	Workshop proposer
Timeframe	depends on level of preparedness	depends on level of preparedness	depends on level of preparedness in case CCMC support needed + 30-45 days more	no deadline, at earliest convenience consultation period with CEN technical body - 30-45 days in case a decision of CEN Technical Body needed + 30-45 days	May take between a few weeks and several months depending on the format	15 days after approval of the Workshop description form, CCMC publishes the post on its website. Interested parties may comment within 30 days	n/a	according to the timetable agreed by the Workshop participants; in case of consultation with relevant technical bodies, commenting period of 30 days	30 days optional, but recommended phase	CWA is published as soon as possible after approval

Additional information

Validity period

A CWA is valid for 3 years. When the 3-year period passes and after relevant consultations, several options exist: the CWA can be confirmed for another 3 years, or revised, or withdrawn, or converted into another deliverable by a CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Body.

After 6 years from initial publication, even where the CWA has been revised during this time, the CWA is either proposed for conversion into another deliverable (this could happen at any time during the 6-year period) or submitted by CCMC to the CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Boards for decision regarding its withdrawal.

Copyrights

The CEN-CENELEC policy on copyright, exploitation right and distribution of all CEN-CENELEC publications, applies to CWAs, in accordance with CEN and CENELEC Guide 10.

The CWA is a collaborative copyright work composed by a set of independent, original inputs from experts. CEN and CENELEC are the sole owners of the rights to reproduce the CWA.

For any pre-existing works being included in the CWA, the experts are requested to grant the necessary rights to their contributions to CEN and/or CENELEC.

Any of these granted rights does not preclude an expert from continuing to use pre-existing copyright works owned by him/her (or the respective employer).

In cases where a pre-existing copyright work is owned by a third-party and proposed for incorporation by an expert, it must be ensured that the appropriate rights are granted to CEN and/or CENELEC.

In case of matters related to patents, CEN-CENELEC Guide 8 on Guidelines for Implementation of the Common IPR Policy on Patents applies.

The standardization process through CWA could be visualized as follows:

CWA Development Procedure

Figure 9. CWA Development Pathway

3. ROADMAP FOR STANDARDIZATION THROUGH EUROPEAN TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT (ETA) AND DEVELOPMENT OF EUROPEAN ASSESSMENT DOCUMENT (EAD)

1. Action 1: Clearly define innovation product and prepare

WHAT

Check the information on the EOTA website – <https://www.eota.eu/> and find information relevant to your product and intention.

Prepare all necessary technical documents. The innovator will be requested to submit a manufacturer's technical file (MTF) with detailed information on your product, its intended use, as well as details of the factory production control you as manufacturer intends to apply.

Check the available ETAs/EADs (<https://www.eota.eu/eads>) and if there are not appropriate ones for the specific product assessment, consider the possibility of EAD development.

WHO

The manufacturer.

TIME

Proposal of a timeframe is not relevant, as this depends entirely on the level of preparedness.

2. Action 2: Initiate the procedure

WHAT

Choose a responsible Technical Assessment Body (TAB) from EOTA network to guide you through the entire ETA/EAD procedure. The TAB should be designated for the relevant product area. Be informed that an ETA can't be requested directly to EOTA.

Prepare and send to the TAB a request for European Technical Assessment (ETA) for the innovative construction product. The request should provide information on the type and description of the construction product; its essential characteristics and intended use; indication if the construction product is not or not fully covered by a harmonized standard or an EAD; declaration that an application has not been introduced to another TAB before.

EOTA advises, when it comes to innovations, to enter dialogue with the reference TAB before investing to a great extent in testing.

The TAB will check the request form and will provide its general terms and a quotation. The manufacturer is required to sign a service contract with the chosen TAB, which, by this, becomes the responsible TAB (RTAB). Commercial confidentiality agreements are an available option.

The ETA request will be registered by EOTA.

If a new EAD needs to be developed for the ETA or an existing one amended EOTA will launch the procedure for that.

WHO

This stage is under the manufacturer's responsibility, assisted by the RTAB.

TIME

If adequate preparation is undertaken beforehand, the duration of this stage can be minimized.

3. Action 3: Collaborate at the start of the EAD development

WHAT

For the development of a new EAD, EOTA will launch a consultation among member TABs designated for the relevant product area and will set up a working group. The RTAB will become the main drafter of the EAD, but other TABs designated for the product area can also contribute actively to the elaboration and comment at different stages of the development process.

The RTAB and the EOTA working group will develop a work and assessment programme.

The RTAB shall ensure that the manufacturer's feedback and wishes are taken into consideration. A contract is signed between the manufacturer and the responsible TAB containing key elements of the working programme, organization at EOTA level and TABs contributing to the EAD development. The contract is the actual starting point of the EAD development procedure.

When the final work programme is agreed among all competent TABs for the relevant product area EOTA informs the European Commission about it providing the details of the request and the assessment programme to be followed.

WHO

The main responsibility here is borne by the RTAB and EOTA. In this phase, the manufacturer's role is relatively passive, primarily involving collaboration with the selected Technical Assessment Body (TAB).

TIME

Reaching agreement on the final work programme usually takes no more than **three months** after the initiation of the procedure.

4. Action 4: Contribute to the EAD development

WHAT

The RTAB shall prepare the draft EAD, with contribution and comments from other competent TABs.

Horizontal or ad hoc project teams may also contribute to the development of specific assessment methods or the discussion of assessment approaches where required.

The draft EAD shall be adopted by EOTA after a first consultation with the European Commission and the manufacturer.

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WHO

RTAB and EOTA are responsible for the development and adoption of the draft EAD, but they need to work in close collaboration with the manufacturer.

The manufacturer is expected to contribute to the elaboration, as owner of the innovation and specific know-how holder, and to collaborate closely with the RTAB.

TIME

In general, the development of an EAD takes about six months from the moment of informing the EC of the work programme until its adoption.

The timeframe defined in the CPR for the development of an EAD is 9 months.

However, delays for the finalisation of EU legislative procedures are possible. If the development process is delayed, the manufacturer will be informed as soon as possible.

5. Action 5: Responses to the RTAB for final adoption of the EAD

WHAT

When the final EAD is agreed in the EOTA working group, the responsible TAB will formally submit it to the manufacturer for final comments.

Finally, the draft is adopted by EOTA's Technical Board and submitted for official observations to the EC. If no comments are received within 15 working days or once the comments received have been handled, the EAD is considered adopted by EC.

This Adopted EAD will become the basis for issuing the ETA.

The RTAB issues the ETA after consultation of all TABs designated for the relevant product areas.

The EAD might be adjusted once more based on the experience gained and lessons learnt.

The final version will then be formally adopted as Final EAD by EOTA. The final EAD version will be submitted to the EC for publication of its reference in the Official Journal of the European Union.

WHO

RTAB, EOTA and the European Commission are responsible for the finalization of the procedure, the manufacturer should contribute to it and be responsive to the TAB's requests.

TIME

The only pre-defined time limit here is the 15 working days period for EC comments on the final draft of the EAD.

In conclusion on timeframe: On average, the complete ETA procedure takes approximately five months if no EAD needs to be developed.

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If your product is not entirely covered by an existing EAD and a new EAD needs to be developed or an existing one amended, the CPR allows a processing time of nine months for this procedure.

In practice, the actual processing time for an ETA mainly depends on the complexity and scope of the assessment, time required for testing, effectiveness and rapidity of communication between the manufacturer and the RTAB as well prior experience with the procedure.

All the actions are summarized in the table below showing the description of each actions, the responsible persons, supporters and stakeholders as well as the timeframe:

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Table 5. EAD Development Procedure

Action No	1: DEFINE the innovation product and PREPARE	2: INITIATE THE PROCEDURE	3: COLLABORATE AT THE START OF THE EAD DEVELOPMENT	4: CONTRIBUTE TO THE EAD DEVELOPMENT	5: BE RESPONSIVE TO YOUR RTAB FOR FINAL ADOPTION OF THE EAD
Description	Prepare all necessary technical documents, check EOTA website and the available ETAs/EADs, consider the possibility of EAD development	Choose a responsible TAB; prepare and send to the TAB a request for ETA for the construction product; sign a contract; ETA request registered by EOTA. EOTA launches a procedure for new EAD development	EOTA sets up a working group of TABs for EAD development. The RTAB becomes the main drafter of the EAD. The RTAB and the EOTA working group develop a work and assessment programme after a contract is signed between the manufacturer and the RTAB. EOTA informs the EC	The RTAB prepares the draft EAD, with contribution and comments from other competent TABs. The draft EAD is adopted by EOTA after a first consultation with the European Commission and the manufacturer	The final EAD is agreed in the EOTA working group and the responsible TAB submits it to the manufacturer for final comments. The draft is adopted by EOTA's Technical Board and submitted for official observations to the EC. If no comments of the EC are received or once the comments have been handled, the EAD is considered adopted by EC. This Adopted EAD becomes the basis for issuing the ETA. The EAD might be adjusted once more based on the experience gained during the technical assessment. The final version is formally adopted as Final EAD by EOTA and is submitted to the EC for publication of its reference in the OJ.
Responsible	the manufacturer	the manufacturer	RTAB and EOTA	RTAB and EOTA	RTAB, EOTA and the European Commission
Supporters and stakeholders	n/a	RTAB and EOTA	the manufacturer and other competent TABs	the manufacturer	the manufacturer
Timeframe	depends on level of preparedness	in case of good preparation in advance, not too much time	three months after the initiation of the procedure	6-9 months	The only pre-defined time limit here is the 15 working days period for EC comments on the final draft of the EAD

The standardization process through EAD could be visualized as follows:

Figure 10. EAD Development Pathway

BIBLIOGRAPHY AND REFERENCES

CEN-CENELEC website - <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>

CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 “CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreements – A rapid way to standardization”

EOTA website - <https://www.eota.eu/>

AFCOS

Roadmap “Capacity building in standardization of new building materials as a booster of new knowledge in industry”

Project: Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for

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Boosting the Twin Transition

Acronym: AFCOS

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Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	101135855	Acronym	AFCOS
Full Title	Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition		
Call and topic identifier	HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-64		
Duration	24 months		
Start Date	1 November 2023	End date	31 October 2025
Website	www.afcos-project.eu		
Coordinator	Cleantech Bulgaria		

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1.0	01.10.2024		First draft	Technical University Sofia
V2.0	11.10.2024		Review	Cleantech Bulgaria
V3.0	24.10.2024		Review	BDS, CRISCON, RoGBC

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Acknowledgement

This document is a deliverable of AFCOS project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101135855.

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I. APPLICATION OF THE AFCOS METHODOLOGY FOR CO-DESIGN OF ROADMAPS

I.1. Choosing a spiral model: The Quintuple Helix model

The Quintuple Helix model is used to expand interaction between different sectors in order to achieve innovation and sustainable development. In the case of construction products, the model provides a structure for identifying key stakeholders and delivering training.

The Quintuple Helix model covers five main areas that can be identified as key stakeholders in the development of training programs on the basics of standardization and of marketing of innovative construction products.

Fig. 1 The five helices of the quintuple helix model of innovation economics
Source: AFCOS, Methodology for co-design of roadmaps

A. Industry (business sector):

- These must be familiar with the current regulations – legislation, standards and how to place their products (incl. innovative ones) on the market. This can be done by training employees in companies in cooperation with training institutions (VET centres¹ and/or universities, etc.).

¹ **VET center - Vocational education and training** provides learners with essential skills enhancing their employability, supporting their personal development and encouraging active citizenship.

B. Government:

- Government institutions can support and encourage standardization training and innovative programs through policy updates. Any Ministry of Education may include the standardization topic within the vocational education and training (VET) framework in the respective country.

C. Academia (research and educational institutions):

- These could further exploit the roadmap by integrating the topic of standardization in their programs, by developing and conducting training courses on standardization and marketing of innovative construction products. They will be also a target group of the pilot training of the AFCOS project.

D. Society (citizens and non-governmental organisations):

- Through workshops, roundtables, focus groups, information days, mass media, the public shall be informed about the need for training on standardization and the production and use of innovative construction products. They could be active and demand the use of innovative construction products in the process of designing and building new infrastructure - residential buildings, kindergartens, schools, public buildings, etc. This can activate both policy makers and investors.

E. Environment (the natural environment):

- Training on standardization and marketing of innovative construction products will also have added value to environmental protection. The training courses will include topics concerning the application of environmental protection standards.

I.2. The development of the roadmap

This Roadmap has been developed on the basis of the main stages and steps of the Methodology for co-design of Roadmaps developed under the AFCOS project, as well as on the basic principles, stages and steps of the Quintuple Helix model.

Fig. 2 Main stages and steps of roadmap development, AFCOS, Methodology for co-design of roadmaps

The preparation stage involved a thorough analysis of the training needs related to standardization, focusing specifically on the skills required by the identified target groups, which are educational institutions and industry and professionals' associations.

Stakeholder engagement included consultations with educators, industry professionals, and regulatory bodies to gather input on the essential competencies needed for effective training on standardization of new construction products.

In the **generation of ideas** phase, various training methods and curricula were proposed, emphasizing the incorporation of practical applications and real-world scenarios relevant to standardization practices.

The **design phase** focused on structuring the training programs to ensure they are aligned with the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), aiming for levels 5 to 7 for educational institutions and levels 6 to 8 for industry representatives.

Validation and testing is a 2-step process including:

- participatory approach through validation during dedicated stakeholders' consultations – 1 in Bulgaria and 1 in Romania (the 2 piloting countries) with the members of the Multistakeholder Research Group formed under the AFCOS project as well as with other external stakeholders: mainly industrial representatives and educational and training bodies described below;
- pilot training sessions in Bulgaria and Romania with students (master students), industry organizations (and employees), government institutions, agencies and other stakeholders to assess the effectiveness of the proposed curricula and training methods, gathering feedback from participants to refine the content and delivery methods. The refinement phase addressed the feedback, making necessary adjustments to enhance the relevance and applicability of the training programs.

Finally, the **dissemination of the roadmap** involved sharing the finalized training programs and resources with stakeholders, ensuring widespread access and promoting the importance of standardization in enhancing quality and compliance within the construction industry. The training programs will be uploaded to a digital educational platform with the aim to be easily accessible for the potential trainees. The content could be also made available on other official and recognized platforms.

II. GENERAL ROADMAP'S STAGES

The procedure for co-designing a roadmap for capacity building in the standardization of new construction products should be comprehensive and structured to promote collaboration among diverse stakeholders.

1. The first main goal involves **identifying the key actors and stakeholders** who play a crucial role in the development and placement of new building products within the European market. These include, according to AFCOS' Methodology for co-design of roadmaps² industry professionals, government bodies, research institutions, educational

² DEL 3.1. in the AFCOS project under EU GA No 101135855

organizations, and civil society representatives, ensuring that all relevant voices are considered in the process.

2. A thorough **assessment of existing knowledge and the needs of the target groups** must be conducted to identify gaps and weaknesses. This involves evaluating current competencies within the stakeholder groups and recognizing areas where further training or resources are needed. By understanding these deficiencies, targeted training programs can be developed to address specific knowledge gaps effectively.
3. The third objective focuses on **developing a training program** tailored to the needs of target groups, incorporating a variety of training methods, types, and durations that best suit their learning preferences and professional roles. The curriculum should reflect the latest trends and standards in the construction industry, ensuring participants receive relevant and practical knowledge.
4. To ensure the effectiveness of the training program, **mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation** must be established, including setting up criteria for assessing training outcomes and analyzing the results to determine whether the program meets its objectives. Regular feedback from participants can provide valuable insights for continuous improvement.

II.1. STAGE I - IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS AND TARGET GROUPS

The identified stakeholders' needs must be determined to choose the appropriate training methods aimed at their needs and professional roles, as well as the corresponding types of training related to the European Qualifications Framework (EQF).

Group	Educational needs	Type of training	Training method	EQF Level	Stakeholder (5-Helix model)
Group 1. Professionals in the construction sector	Updating knowledge of new technologies, materials and sector-specific standards, sustainable construction, safety standards.	Technical trainings, courses in construction innovations, certification programs.	Seminars, webinars, practical workshops.	Levels 4-8	Industry Academia
Group 2. Construction companies and entrepreneurs	Management of construction processes, efficient use of resources,	Trainings in construction site management, supply chains, logistics.	Project management courses, online platforms.	Levels 6-8	Industry

Group	Educational needs	Type of training	Training method	EQF Level	Stakeholder (5-Helix model)
	regulatory requirements, applicable standards.				
Group 3. Public institutions and regulatory bodies	Legislation, control, and inspections of construction sites, new standards supporting regulation.	Courses in building regulations, legislation, environmental standards, harmonized standards.	Legal seminars, online courses.	Levels 5-6	Government
Group 4. End users	Awareness of new products, energy-efficient solutions.	Awareness sessions on new technologies and products and safety matters of products.	Presentations, webinars, consultations.	Levels 4-5	Civil society
Group 5. Sales representatives and distributors	Knowledge of new products, sales techniques.	Trainings on product characteristics and sales strategies.	Presentations, sales simulations.	Levels 4-5	Industry
Group 6. Professional associations and guilds	Updating professional standards and innovations in the sector.	Professional conferences, certification courses.	Symposia, professional networks.	Levels 5-7	Civil society Industry
Group 7. Educational institutions	Preparation for professional development, knowledge of new technologies.	Theoretical training at universities and vocational schools.	Lectures, practical activities, internships.	Levels 3-8	Academia
Group 8. Consultancy and design companies	Expanding knowledge of new materials and methods, project management.	Trainings in design, construction standards.	Practical courses, webinars, certifications.	Levels 6-8	Industry
Group 9. Insurance companies and risk assessors	Risk assessment in construction, innovations in insurance products.	Courses in risk management.	Online courses, simulations.	Levels 6-7	Industry

Group	Educational needs	Type of training	Training method	EQF Level	Stakeholder (5-Helix model)
Group 10. Environmental organizations	Sustainable construction, green technologies, environmental standards, ESG reporting	Sustainable construction courses and certifications.	Awareness campaigns and seminars, certification courses.	Levels 5-8	Civil society Industry
Group 11. Public and NGOs	Workplace safety control, social responsibility.	Health and safety, social sustainability courses.	Workshops, discussion groups.	Levels 5-6	Civil society Government
Group 12. Investors and financial institutions	Evaluation of construction projects, investment management.	Financial analyses and risk assessment.	Seminars, webinars, simulations.	Levels 6-7	Industry
Group 13. Media and marketing specialists	Promotion of new construction products and innovative solutions, communication strategies.	Marketing and communication training.	Seminars, courses in digital marketing.	Levels 5-6	Civil society

As primary target groups for the AFCOS project Groups 1, 2 and 7 - **Professionals in the construction sector & Construction companies and entrepreneurs** [called for the purposes of the Roadmap “Industry representatives”] and **Educational institutions** [both students and professors included] will be targeted.

These groups are interconnected, for instance - educational institutions often seek to align their curricula with industry requirements, and industry representatives benefit from fresh perspectives and innovative ideas coming from academia. By prioritizing these groups, we can create a feedback loop that enhances educational programs based on industry needs while simultaneously informing industry about practices with insights from educational research.

Group 1 and 2: Industry representatives play a crucial role in implementing changes within the sector; their participation is essential for fostering collaboration between academia and industry. By focusing on this group, the project can directly address the needs of those who influence standards and practices in the construction field. They need constant updating of knowledge about

innovative building products and new technologies in the field – e. g. low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope. They must be familiar with the most current normative documents and standards that govern the construction sector - recent updates in regulations, compliance requirements, and industry's best practices. A deep overview of methodologies for assessing, certifying, and integrating products into construction practices, ensuring compliance with both national and European standards. **Professionals include** (not only) engineers, architects, technicians from manufacturers of new products, companies involved in design, innovative building manufacturers and resellers, quality managers, and sustainability consultants, expected to have a minimum qualification equivalent to EQF Level 4 (e.g., secondary education with vocational training) or higher, ensuring a solid foundational knowledge for advancing to the course's EQF Level 5 content. Individuals with technical education or related fields and a minimum of 2 years of professional experience, with a preference for those working in the construction sector.

Group 7: Educational institutions are crucial in shaping the future workforce of the construction industry, making their engagement vital for long-term sustainability and innovation in the sector. By equipping **students** with knowledge and skills related to standardization and new technologies, we ensure a well-prepared generation ready to meet the industry's evolving demands. Preparation for professional development for students aligned with the latest industry trends and expectations, ensuring they are competitive in the job market. **Professors can** play an essential role in this process by developing curricula that integrate the latest industry practices and research. Their involvement ensures that educational programs are relevant and up-to-date, fostering an environment where students can learn from experienced educators while also encouraging faculty research on innovative construction practices and standardization. Research opportunities for both professors and students enriching both academic and practical knowledge.

The European Qualifications Framework (EQF)

The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) plays a pivotal role in the capacity-building roadmap for the standardization of new construction products, particularly concerning the two identified target groups: educational institutions and industry representatives.

EQF LEVEL 8	ACADEMIC LEVEL	DOCTORATE
EQF LEVEL 7		MASTER
EQF LEVEL 6	POST UPPER SECONDARY LEVEL	BACHELOR
EQF LEVEL 5		HIGHER NATIONAL DIPLOMA
EQF LEVEL 4	UPPER SECONDARY LEVEL	HIGHER NATIONAL CERTIFICATE, UPPER SECONDARY DIPLOMA
EQF LEVEL 3	SECONDARY LEVEL	SECONDARY DIPLOMA OR VOCATIONAL DIPLOMA
EQF LEVEL 2	PRIMARY LEVEL	SECONDARY SCHOOL WITH NO DIPLOMA
EQF LEVEL 1		PRIMARY SCHOOL

Fig. 3 EQF Levels. source <https://www.maintworld.com/>

For **educational institutions**, the targeted entry level for participants are primarily 5 and 6 (when not 7 by regulatory provisions, as for licensed professionals), focusing on enhancing their curriculum to include technical skills for standardization and analytical skills. This will empower students with the necessary competencies to navigate European and international standards, ensuring their future employability and readiness to engage in the construction industry.

Industry representatives, on the other hand, can be participants with EQF Levels 5, 6 and 7, which encompasses more advanced skills. This includes the ability to oversee standardization processes, manage compliance with evolving regulations, and leverage digital tools for quality control. Through targeted training programs, these professionals will not only update their knowledge of innovative construction products and standards/standardization deliverables but also enhance their capabilities in leading change and implementing sustainable practices in their organizations.

Both groups will benefit from the roadmap's emphasis on green building certifications, ensuring that they are well-versed in environmentally friendly practices and standards. The skills and knowledge gained will equip the trainees with the minimum level of autonomy corresponding to EQF Level 7. This approach ensures that the trainees not only acquire relevant skills but also contribute meaningfully to the advancement of sustainable construction practices in the EU.

II.2. STAGE II - SKILLS TO BE ACQUIRED BY THE TARGETED GROUPS

The skills to be acquired by the trainees, based on the identified needs of the two target groups - educational institutions and industry representatives – include a range of competencies essential for effective participation in the construction industry, particularly in the context of standardization.

For the **Educational institutions**, the skill set focus on equipping future professionals with the necessary knowledge and tools.

- Firstly, **technical skills** for standardization are vital. Trainees will learn to work with European and national standards, specifically tailored for the construction products sector. They will also be trained to prepare documentation for product certification, emphasizing market placement. Additionally, students will gain competencies in conducting tests and evaluations of new products based on defined requirement of European Regulations (CPR) and global market standards, aligning with EQF Level 5 or above where appropriate.
- **Analytical skills** are crucial for this group, as they shall develop the ability to analyze test results and assess compliance with standard requirements. These include digital data management for compliance tracking, which shall empower them to compare new materials and technologies based on innovative standards and environmental requirements.
- **Communication skills** will also be considered, enabling students to effectively convey standardization requirements and to clearly articulate technical descriptions. They will learn to compose reports and certification related documentation that ensure regulatory compliance across various markets, equipping them with the ability to engage with future employers and stakeholders effectively.

For **Industry representatives**, the skill set focuses on practical application and management within the construction sector. Updating knowledge about innovative construction products and new technologies is major for industry representatives. Training sessions will cover the benefits and applications of innovative products, including low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope where relevant.

- **Management skills** will be critical for this group, as trainees will learn about managing standards implementation and compliance processes within their organizations. This includes coordinating with quality control teams and dealing with change management efforts for implementing new standards. They will also learn about implementation plans for new standards, monitor compliance and engage with stakeholders such as clients and regulatory bodies, aiming at EQF Level 5 and above according to the entrance level.
- **Digital skills** are increasingly important for industry representatives as well. Learning to utilize digital tools for quality control and document management will enhance their ability to ensure traceability and transparency in standards compliance.

In summary, these skill sets for both target groups shall collectively prepare trainees to contribute effectively to the evolving needs of the construction industry, particularly regarding innovative and sustainable practices.

II.3. STAGE III - DEVELOPING OF TRAINING PROGRAM

The objective of the training is to educate the two identified prioritised **target groups** in the field of standardization of new construction products, introducing participants to modern methods for evaluation and certification, legislative requirements, new technologies, and environmental standards. The training will emphasize the application of standardization in the context of emerging construction products and sustainable construction practices.

The courses aim to align with an entry level of the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) and relevant National Qualifications Frameworks (NQFs) to ensure that the skills and knowledge gained are recognized and valued across European industries.

II.3.1. Definition of core modules

A. Introduction to standardization.

Fundamentals of standards and standardization, including., including the role of standards

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in innovation and assurance of conformity assessment in the construction products sector.

B. Innovations in new materials and products.

Focused on the latest trends in sustainable construction materials, such as bio-based materials, advanced composites, and recyclable materials.

C. Testing of new products.

Practical methods for evaluating the durability, safety, and performance of new materials, with industry-specific examples such as insulation materials and eco-friendly alternatives.

D. Quality management.

Techniques for implementing quality management systems, including ISO 9001 and ISO 14001, and adapting them for new product development in construction.

E. Environmental standards.

Deep dive into green building certifications can be used to frame the environmental compatibility of new materials.

F. Application of digital technologies.

Advanced digital tools for predictive quality analysis of product standards.

G. Additional focus areas.

- **Climate adaptation and resilience** - How new materials can be standardized to meet the challenges of climate-resilient construction.
- **Global and sector-specific standards overview** - Comparative analysis of European standards supporting the Single market.

II.3.2. Preparation of a schedule

A. Course duration – To be based on target groups and their needs and skills gaps and training outcomes, divided into theory and practical sessions. Blended learning approach with live sessions and self-paced tasks components.

B. Teaching methods - lectures, practical tasks, industry-specific case studies, tests, self-assessment, and workshops. **Live sessions** are, by default, conducted via appropriate electronic platforms. **Online content** (video lectures, reading materials, and quizzes) is available on a learning management system (LMS) such as Moodle or Google Classroom for participants to access at their convenience. **Language:** to be defined based on the target groups and effectiveness.

C. Hybrid model of training:

- **Theoretical part** - online lectures, seminars, and video tutorials on global standardization practices.
- **Practical part** - combination of remote tasks and in-person lab sessions for practical testing and certification simulations of new materials.

- **Internship or mentorship opportunities** - collaboration with companies for internships or mentorship, enabling participants to apply their skills directly in industry settings.
 - **Flexible participation** - synchronous and asynchronous sessions to accommodate participants with varying schedules.
- D. Training outcomes** - acquisition of knowledge in standardization, practical skills for evaluating new products, participant certification, and ability to apply skills in real-world scenarios.

Sessions Schedule

I. Theory – Introduction and standardization

Focus: Understanding the fundamentals of standardization, exploring European and national standards and their application in industries.

Session 1: Overview of standardization - introduction to the standards development process, European, EU and national standards and other standardization deliverables (incl. CWA and EAD). The importance of standardization for innovation.

Session 2: Industry-specific practices - case studies on standardization in sectors like construction, manufacturing, and execution of construction works. How standards impact market access and product safety and sustainability

Session 3: Legislation and compliance - overview of legal requirements for product certification and the relationship between standardization and regulatory frameworks in the EU and other markets.

Activities: Lessons, interactive Q&A sessions, discussion boards for peer engagement, and a quiz to assess understanding of the standards landscape.

II. Practice – Innovative products and materials.

Focus: Practical training on evaluating innovative products and new materials, with a focus on sustainability and technologies.

Session 1: Practical workshop on material evaluation - hands-on evaluation of new materials like eco-friendly composites, advanced insulation, and recycled materials. Participants will conduct a virtual lab exercise using provided datasets.

Session 2: Simulated real-world scenarios - group exercises involving simulated scenarios, such as assessing the durability and characteristics of new materials and products or evaluating a new energy-efficient product.

Session 3: Innovation and standards - exploring how standards /standardization deliverables can foster innovation and support the market entry of new products. Participants will prepare a brief report on a chosen innovative product and its standardization needs.

Activities: Case study analyses, virtual breakout rooms for group work, and submission of a mini

report on a selected material or product.

III. Theory – Quality management and control

Focus: Delving into quality management principles and digital tools that support product standardization.

Session 1: Quality assurance frameworks - Introduction to quality management systems (QMS) and the role of these frameworks in maintaining high product standards.

Session 2: Digital tools for quality control - Training on software tools for product documentation and analysis for quality testing.

Session 3: Integrating sustainability into quality control - Focus on environmental standards and best practices for ensuring sustainability throughout the product lifecycle.

Activities: Hands-on demonstration software for documenting product specifications, exercises in analysis results, and a group discussion on sustainable quality practices.

IV. Final test and practical task

Focus: Application of knowledge gained throughout the course, with an emphasis on developing a practical standardization plan.

Session 1: Review and preparation - recap of key concepts covered in previous modules and guidance on how to tackle the final task.

Session 2: Practical task - participants are assigned to develop a comprehensive standardization plan for a new product, considering aspects like material selection, product characteristics, test methods, factory production and quality control, environmental compliance, and use of digital tools.

Session 3: Simulate a Workshop on a CWA for an innovative solution in the construction sector

Session 4: Final assessment and feedback - participants present their standardization plans to peers and instructors. This session includes peer review and personalized feedback from instructors.

Activities. Submission of the final project, peer feedback sessions, and self-assessment surveys to reflect on the learning process.

Final Test. A comprehensive quiz covering the theoretical components, along with an open-ended section where participants justify their approach to the standardization plan.

Practical Task. Developing a standardization plan, including a summary of compliance with relevant standards or other standardizations deliverables, use of sustainable practices, and integration of digital solutions.

II.3.3. Selection of trainers

Specialists with experience in the industry of new products, standardization, certification, and quality management, with a background in sustainable materials and digital transformation, like:

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- Professionals with deep knowledge of the latest developments in innovative products, including sustainable construction products and eco-friendly technologies.
- Specialists who have led standardization processes in various industries, particularly in construction, manufacturing, and product testing. Their expertise includes working with European and national standards.
- Experts with a background in implementing quality assurance frameworks and conducting quality audits.
- Professionals with experience in digital transformation strategies for the construction and product development sectors for product analysis of sustainable materials.

Proven experience and knowledge on teaching adult learners, and working with innovations' implementation, like:

- Professional experience in relevant industries such as standardization, certification, and quality management, with practical expertise in working with innovation and sustainable materials.
- Academic degrees in engineering, materials science, environmental management, or business administration, with additional qualifications in adult education and training methods.
- Specialization in Green building / infrastructure certifications: knowledge and hands-on experience with green building / infrastructure standards ensuring that course content aligns with industry best practices for sustainable development.
- Skills in digital education: Familiarity with e-learning platforms and virtual teaching tools, enabling them to deliver engaging online sessions and workshops.

II.3.4. Teaching methods selection

Teaching Methods: Lecturing, mentorship, practical task consultations, evaluation of case studies, and guidance on implementing new standards in real-world settings.

- **Lectures** - instructors provide structured presentations on key topics such as international and European standards, quality management frameworks, and digital tools. These lectures include visual aids, real-world examples, and case studies to illustrate complex concepts.
- **Practical task consultations** - instructors provide direct support during practical sessions, guiding participants as they work on hands-on tasks such as material evaluations or the development of a standardization plan. These consultations are designed to help participants overcome challenges and ensure the practical applicability of their solutions.
- **Evaluation of case studies** - the teaching team curates and evaluates real-world case studies related to standardization, quality control, and the certification of innovative products. Participants analyze these cases, learn to identify best practices, and discuss alternative solutions with their peers and instructors.
- **Guidance on implementing** new standards in real-world settings - Instructors provide step-by-step guidance on how to integrate new standards into existing workflows, emphasizing compliance with industry regulations and adaptation to evolving market demands. This

includes simulation implementation exercises, where participants simulate the process of adopting a new standard in their workplace.

- **Interactive teaching** - the team uses interactive methods like virtual breakout rooms, discussion boards, and live Q&A sessions to foster collaboration and peer learning. This approach ensures participants remain engaged and can apply theoretical concepts through group activities and problem-solving sessions.
 - **Selection of a digital platform**
 - Platform with capabilities for video-conferencing lectures (e.g., Zoom, MS Teams).
 - Support for electronic learning materials, tests, and assessments (e.g. Moodle, Google Classroom).
 - Interactive communication – forums and chats for questions and discussions.
- Advantages:** Facilitates access to learning materials, video lectures, and self-assessments, and allows for interactive sessions with industry experts.
- Additional Requirement:** Integration with industry-specific software for practical simulations during the course.

II.3.5. Dissemination of the training

- Promotion channels - social media, organization's website, the life-long or distance learning centres at the universities, professional platforms (e.g., LinkedIn), and participation in green building and innovation forums.
- Informational materials - infographics, presentations, videos, interviews with instructors, and success stories from course alumni.
- Participation in events - presenting the course at industry-specific exhibitions and conferences, focusing on sustainable construction.
- Marketing strategy - use of targeted email campaigns, partnerships with industry associations, and incentives for early registration and group participation.

II.3.6. Definition of assessment criteria

An assessment framework that includes tests, self-assessments, and a final project, designed to evaluate participants' progress and understanding in standardization training and providing personalized feedback for improvement.

1. **Tests and case studies.** Each module concludes with a brief test and/or practical case study, including industry-specific scenarios like testing innovative materials for energy efficiency.
2. **Self-assessment.** Participants complete self-assessment surveys after each module to analyze their development and identify areas for improvement.
3. **Final assessment.** Final project requires developing a standardization plan for a new building material, focusing on environmental compatibility and digital integration.
4. **Feedback.** Personalized feedback from instructors and peer reviews.

II.3.7. Setting of completion requirements

Minimum attendance requirement - at least 80% of the lectures and 90% of practical sessions, with flexibility for those participating in mentorship programs, monitored through participation in person or through the electronic platform.

Participants will be duly certified when:

- Successful completion of all modules and tests.
- Completion of a final project that meets sustainability and innovation standards.
- Professional qualification certificates will be issued to participants who meet the criteria, with special recognition for those who excel in implementing innovative standardization practices.
- Participants who successfully complete all modules and the final project will gain skills and knowledge allowing them to reach level of autonomy corresponding to EQF Level 5 or above depending on the entrance level and the typology of the training. This ensures a positive contribution towards spreaded valid capacities across European and national contexts for professionals in standardization.

II.4. STAGE IV - INDICATORS FOR EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOMES

To ensure the effectiveness of the training program, it is crucial to establish robust mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation. This process involves defining clear criteria for assessing the outcomes of the training and analyzing the results to verify whether the program meets its set objectives.

One of the fundamental components of this mechanism is **gathering regular feedback from participants**, which can offer valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the program, allowing for continuous improvements and adjustments. This feedback can also highlight aspects of the training that resonate well with participants, as well as areas needing enhancement to better meet their needs.

One of the key indicators of the training program's success is **the percentage of participants who demonstrate an increased understanding of standardization processes** by the end of the course. This can be measured through pre- and post-training assessments, quizzes, or practical exercises that test participants' comprehension. Another important metric is the number of successfully completed practical tasks and case studies, which provide a real-world context for applying standardization knowledge.

A critical outcome to monitor is the application of the acquired knowledge in **real professional situations** post-course. This includes observing how participants integrate the new skills into their daily work activities, particularly in relation to standardization processes and the development of new building products. Monitoring the percentage of participants who earn a certificate for successfully completing the course is another valuable metric.

Ensuring that the required EQFs align with National Qualifications Frameworks (NQFs) which

guarantees that the program is of high quality for participants who seek to validate their skills and knowledge beyond their local context, will provide them with opportunities for professional mobility and career growth.

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III. APPLICABILITY OF THE ROADMAP “Capacity building in standardization of new construction products as a booster of new knowledge in industry”

The applicability of the roadmap for training in standardization extends beyond the scope of the AFCOS project, offering a valuable framework for the broader construction industry and other sectors that rely on standardization processes and innovative building products. Its structured approach is highly adaptable, making it **suitable for various contexts**, including national and European training initiatives.

The roadmap’s approach ensures that the skills and knowledge gained through the training programs can be applied across borders, facilitating mobility and cooperation between professionals in different countries. This adaptability allows the roadmap to be **used by other organizations, educational institutions, and industry bodies** that aim to improve the skills of their workforce in areas such as quality control, product certification, and compliance with both national and European standards.

Beyond the immediate focus on new building products, the roadmap serves as a versatile tool for any industry facing technological change and needing to align with evolving regulatory frameworks. For example, it can support sectors like renewable energy, manufacturing, and digital technologies where **standardization is critical to market access and product innovation**. Trainees can directly apply their newfound expertise in real-world scenarios, making the training relevant not only for their professional development but also for the competitiveness of their organizations. The roadmap's mechanisms for **monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness** of the training ensure that it remains dynamic, capable of evolving in response to new industry trends and stakeholder needs. This makes it a sustainable model for fostering a culture of standardization and innovation across a variety of sectors, ensuring that they can adapt to both current challenges and future opportunities.

IV. PILOT TRAININGS (WITHIN THE AFCOS PROJECT)

For the purposes of AFCOS project two training courses will be developed and piloted in two different countries (Bulgaria and Romania) – one for **Educational institutions** and one for the **Industry representatives**.

- **Part One** includes two modules with general information and process of standardization, standardizing construction products and innovations.
- **Part Two** is focused on the specific products targeted by the AFCOS project – “*low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products*” and “*bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope*” as examples on how to standardize such an innovative product implementing the Standardization Roadmap developed under the AFCOS project.

The topics of main interest for the target groups have been identified in the first phase of the AFCOS project (Analysis of pre-normative approach for new building products, incl. legislative, standardization and market context) during several Multistakeholder Research Group meetings. Some of them are common for all stakeholders, others are specific since the project focus is different for both piloting countries - Bulgaria and Romania.

Each of the courses will have its specifics according to the target group and based on the stages above. Modules will be chosen according to the target groups and their duration will be appointed according to the skills needs of every group.

THE STANDARDIZATION OF INNOVATIONS - UNDERSTANDING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF IMPLEMENTING STANDARDS. LEGISLATION. PROCESS OF STANDARDS DEVELOPMENT AND ADOPTION.

Part one – general information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry

Module 1: Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization

Topic 1: Essence and importance of European technical legislation

Topic 2: Legislative acts of the European Union - regulations, directives, decisions, etc.

Topic 3: Requirements of the Construction Products Regulation

Topic 4: Basic concepts of standardization. Types of standards and standard deliverables, status and functions of standards

Topic 5: Mechanism for "conditional obligation" of standards

Topic 6: Awareness of new products

Practical application to case studies on the topics

Module 2: Product responsibility and market surveillance

Topic 1: Conformity assessment, concepts and criteria

Topic 2: Documentation of conformity assessment. Principles of CE marking

Topic 3: Products for CE marking
Topic 4: Declaration of performance and Technical documentation
Topic 5: Product Liability and Consumer Protection
Topic 6: European market surveillance legislation
Practical application to case studies on the topics

Module 3: Green & Digital Transition

Topic 1: Carbon footprint (LCA calculation)
Topic 2: Circular economy
Topic 3: Green buildings certifications
Topic 4: ESG
Topic 5: Green financing

Part two – Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope

Module 3: How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”.

Topic 1: Technological features of innovative building products - low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope.

Topic 2: Next-generation construction products: filling knowledge gaps for construction products’ producers, construction companies and designers.

Topic 3: Understanding new standards: preparing construction stakeholders (product manufacturers, designers, building control and assessment bodies) for evolving building products requirements. Understanding standards and the role of national standardization bodies.

Topic 4: Navigating European market access - understanding EAD, ETA, hEN and the need for harmonized standards, costs and preparation timelines. CWA simulation: standards development for market access.

Topic 5: Eco-design regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1781) and the Digital product passport acc. to Construction Products Regulation (CPR)

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AFCOS

Annex III Feedback summary from the consultation process with external stakeholders

Project: Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Acronym: AFCOS

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Part I. Summary of the feedback received on the Roadmap “Standardization as enabler of innovation uptake in the new building materials field”

The consultation process on the roadmap has been conducted during two online meetings (21.11.2024 and 28.11.2024) with more than 40 participants in total. Key aspects include:

Challenges

- The EU standardization process takes up to 3 years, which does not meet the needs of fast-paced innovation.
- Need to balance product reliability with faster commercialization.

Recommendations

- Development of flexible standards to allow rapid adaptation and implementation of new technologies.
- Participation of industry experts, manufacturers and researchers in joint working groups to accelerate processes.

Conclusions:

- Flexible standardization is essential for innovation, and it must be supported by effective cooperation mechanisms and clear regulatory frameworks.
- There is a need for coordinated action between industry, educational institutions, small and medium-sized enterprises and the public sector focused on the following main priorities:
 - 1. Education and training**
 - Introducing standardization in university programs, especially at master's level.
 - Creating training courses for SMEs to prepare them to work with new standards.
 - 2. Improving standardization processes**
 - Using flexible standardization tools (as both proposed in the roadmap) to facilitate the implementation of innovations.
 - Creating support networks between industry, regulators and research organizations.
 - 3. Sustainable development**
 - Promoting green technologies and integrating environmental standards.
 - Ensuring regulatory and market support for eco-innovation.
 - 4. Stakeholder collaboration**
 - Industry, public institutions and educational institutions should work together to respond to market needs and standards.

- Raising awareness and training of all stakeholders to effectively use standardization as a development tool.
- Coordinated implementation of these steps will lead to a better prepared sector, able to adapt to the challenges of modern construction technologies and regulations.

Feedback from stakeholder

“The solutions in the roadmap appear to be practically applicable and can facilitate the introduction of new construction products to the market. In this regard, it is necessary to disseminate the roadmap among all stakeholders at the national level”

Part II. Summary of the feedback received on the Roadmap “Capacity building in standardization of new building materials as a booster of new knowledge in industry”

Two meetings were held with stakeholders in Bulgaria (29.10.2024) and Romania (28.10.2024) with more than 50 participants in total. During the discussions, the following **main challenges** were identified:

- Low motivation and interest in the construction sector, especially among young people.
- High staff turnover, which makes long-term training difficult.
- Rapid technological changes and lack of qualified personnel.
- Low awareness of the benefits of green construction.
- Lack of practical training (incl. in secondary education) and young professionals.
- Discrimination against people over 50 and limited opportunities for them.
- Lack of regulatory framework for internal training.
- Insufficient incentives to promote the connection between science and business.
- Insufficient focus on practical skills in VET.
- Curricula in higher education do not match industry innovations.

The stakeholders shared some **recommendations for improvement** in 3 main directions:

1. Reskilling and upskilling initiatives:

- Increasing practical training and internships.
- Improvement of curricula in cooperation with business.
- Financial incentives for companies to participate in training programs.

2. Role of stakeholders:

- Industry: Participate in defining skills needs and offering internships.
- Politicians: Develop national standards for training and qualifications.
- Education: Update curricula and strengthen the connection with business.

3. Collaboration:

- Active participation of associations, federations and the construction chambers to promote knowledge and exchange of good practices.

Based on that the main **conclusions** from the consultation process are:

- Coordinated collaboration between government, industry and education is needed to address the challenges identified.
- Combining the efforts of all stakeholders will contribute to building a more skilled, innovative and sustainable workforce that meets the rapidly changing needs of the sector.

